

Changing Environment of Libraries and its Impact towards Marketing of Library and Information Services

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Received : 03/04/2022 1st BPR : 18/04/2022 2nd BPR : 29/04/2022 Accepted : 11/05/2022

Abstract

This paper attempts to study the marketing library and information services in academic libraries in India. Academic libraries plays a vital role in every institution by offering services to their users which comprises of academic staff, undergraduate students, postgraduate students, researchers, non-academic staff and many other users in the academic community. Library management interacts with the environment and is also influenced by it. Library management gets input, energy and materials from the environment. Library and Information Services managers need to be constantly active to be effective and efficient in the changing environment. As study concludes with that library user is very essential part of any academic library in the world. Users are the most important in any library environment because the aim of every academic library is to provide excellent services to the users.

Key words: Libraries, Information, Services, Academic, Users.

Introduction

Marketing of library and information services is an exchange relationship, a process providing mutual benefit to both parties in the negotiation that is librarian and user. The most widely certain beliefs are about library and information services “to provide the right information to the right user at the right time”. This involves diminishing barriers to access and use information and selecting users in making use of their own, particularly with the use of modern technologies.

Marketing help us the following aims of the library and information services:

- A focal point is on the users own purpose and on helping the individual user to express these at every level.
- A focus on the users, giving them an environment in which they can sit, study, work and on giving them an experience of good service.
- A belief that every individual user has different needs, requirements and expectations when user visits/approaches the library. A responsibility to helping the user in compliance skills in obtaining the information from various sources and means.

Figure 1: Relationship between library services and the customer

The 5Ps in Marketing of Library and Information services were as:

- Product: Information resources and research services.
- Price: Free to employees.
- Place: Not necessarily a physical location anymore. A strong web existence is necessary. Libraries are essential as well as physical spaces now and the capabilities in both these worlds are infinite.
- Promotion: Internal bulletins, e-mails, the company intranet, the library web site, newsletters and poster campaigns are all powerful promotional vehicles for displaying new tools and advertising events.
- People (Staff): Staff is comparatively a new element in marketing mix as its importance for the development of strategies has only recently been accomplished. That is why marketing experts now talk about "internal marketing", emphasizing that the entire staff must be at all costs involved in the
- organization's marketing strategies. For the library to remain competitive, or even more essentially.

Objective of The Study

- To study the external and internal environment in which a library works.
- To determine the strategies used in marketing information products and services in academic libraries.

Review of Literature

Das, B. K., & Karn, S. K. (2008), the researcher here studies in dealing with the marketing of library and information services in the global era. It discusses about the marketing perception of today's library and information centers covering various topics such as management of libraries and responsibility to customer's satisfaction. The study also defines the marketing and its current approach to library and information services at the global level. It also describes customer/user's topic such as customer's preference, assumptions, individuality responsiveness, and relationships, quality of services, professional skills and aptitude along with value added services. The marketing should aim at effective library and information services.

The "service trilogy", that is users (customers), the staff (service provider) and information resources and system should be taken care of from the view of these services. Gupta, D. K. (2003), the study portrays that Libraries and information centers are facing a time of remarkable change and challenge in growing technological world. Recent technological developments are creating new forms of information, new sources of information and new ways of providing information from traditional institutions like libraries. There has been an increasing pressure on libraries to organize resources and become autonomous. Library users are revolutionize into customers with rising expectations, diverse needs and wants, and choices. Now, the real invite competition for library and information professionals is not to manage the collection, staff and technology but to turn these resources into services. The notion of services has also changed, from basic to value added, from staff assisted to self-service, from in-house to have it all over, from free to priced, from reactive to pro-active, and from mass reshape to definite service.

External and Internal Environment in Which Library Works

Library management collaborates with the environment and is also changed by it. Library management gets input, energy and materials from the environment. Library and Information Services managers need to be regularly active to be effective and efficient in the changing environment. The overall environment, in which a library works, can be divided into two categories namely external and internal.

Figure 2: Showing factors affecting external environment of the Library and Information Services

External stress on libraries come from the changes taking place outside the library world. It may be seen in context of local, regional and international impact on libraries and information centres. The different dimensions (see Figure 2) for example, economic, technological and socio-political dimensions illustrate conditions and events that have the potential to influence the organisation in many ways. Technology is crucial to the business of every organisation. Technologies offer better featured products, needs less space but more capital and skills. The most noticeable developments are in the fields of information communication and networking technologies. They are used for clarification, storage, betterment and communication of large volume of information across geographical zones within no time. New technologies offer new and improved services in a variety of ways, such as:

- Creation of new or improved services.
- More involvement of users/customers in operational tasks by offering self service system.
- Bridging the gap between small and large libraries as IT provides an opportunity to use the resources, services, products from remote locations through resource sharing and networking.
- Accessible data bank, which would be helpful in recognizing the users' information needs in a better way. Need recognition helps in strengthening relations with the users.
- Globalisation has resulted in ease of access to information around the world, round the clock. Many national and international information networks exist for free flow of information. The globalisation of information has created the quality consciousness among users and has also increased the expectations of the user groups to a great extent.
- Modern communication infrastructures make possible service delivery at global level;
- The increasing reliance on IT in offering services not only globalizes but also provides opportunities to know the services offered globally; and
- The changing nature of services due to advancement in technologies, which are radically altering the methods by which library and information centres can globalise their services.

Economic Dimensions:

New economic thinking has resulted in diverse changes. Public sector enterprises involved in health, insurance, banking, telecommunications, public transport, universities and libraries are under hazard and the governments of most of the countries now prefer as a matter of social as well as economic policies allows privatisation. In today's globalised era library and information centres are unable to maintain their procurement and services at previous level with the finances made available by the state agencies, which has been cut down or have remained fixed for the last many years. A major portion of the library budget goes for the staff salary and it has become very difficult for libraries and information centres to cope up with the rising cost of literature with limited budget for acquisition.

Similarly, there has been a great necessity of funds for acquisition of newer technologies to enhance service capabilities and output of products. There is also a threat from competitors to maintain quality services, as in market economy public and private sectors would coexist for free flow of information.

Commercial firms engaged in production of information and its Marketing of Information Services organisation and retrieval would also charge for such services. Thus, the main challenges before libraries and information centers managers are to:

- Utilize resources properly and efficiently;
- Mobilize resources to meet financial needs; and
- Make services and products qualitative and competitive through accountability.

This has put libraries to market their services and products and charge for value added services, to enter into joint ventures and alliances and to bring operational efficiency and effectiveness, etc. Socio-political Dimensions: The process of democratization at the grass root level in the form of local bodies at village, block and district level, policies of up-liftment of weaker sections of the society, concept of social justice, total literacy campaign, etc. are leading to the change in people's attitude, habits, value and belief. At the same time, disinvestment policies of the governments affect ownership share of the enterprise and their libraries are to take the initiatives in tune with the organization they serve.

Such initiatives are needed with regards to goal-setting, developing vision, building cooperation, responding and reacting to the new situations in the new environment. Many of the library and information centres have taken serious initiatives and have attempted to serve in such an environment. Many are yet to formulate their response to the changing environment. They need to think through their vision, goals and objectives, organisational culture, organisational and functional strategies, etc.

Figure 3: Showing factors affecting internal environment of Library and Information Services

Alongside external dimensions of environmental changes, there are also internal dimensions which library and information managers need to take into account. The internal dimensions include physical resources, systems and people. The whole spectrum is shown in the following Figure 3. All the internal resources, for example, human, finance, information systems and procedures, rules, technology, facilities, etc. are there to serve users better. Thus, the important elements of the internal environment may broadly be grouped into three, namely physical resources, systems and people. These are influenced greatly by user's choices, preferences and needs.

Customers: User is considered the king around whom all activities of the library revolve, library and information centres exist to meet the needs of all its users, user is the focal point of all information activities and library and information centres are incomplete without users. It is mainly because of central position of user in all components of the library. User is "the most important entity in all kinds

of libraries- public, academic and special. User may be a reader, patron, customer, client or anyone who makes the use of services in a library set-up.”

Physical Resources: The most important dimension of the service quality that represents evaluative criteria being used by users are physical facilities, information sources, equipment, communication material, etc. These are required for the comfort of users to sit and study in the library and for producing value-based services /products for them. All aspects of physical facilities must be planned and maintained to ensure convenience, safety, cleanliness and comfort. Information resources must be exhaustive, up-to-date, and balanced in order to provide pin-pointed and timely delivery of information and services with the help of modern equipment. Cozy and inviting atmosphere of the library will attract users to come again and again and value-based services will ensure increased satisfaction among them. The concept of library is changing to the extent of library without walls. Library services offered online must also address the requirements of the users and geared towards meeting them efficiently.

Systems: In a library, systems comprise of the service operations, where inputs are processed and the elements of the service products are created and service is delivered. Activities include classification, cataloguing, indexing, charging and discharging, rules and regulations. Every system and procedure must be designed and operated to meet the needs of users, aiming at making simplicity in use, accuracy, reliability, timeliness, completeness, etc. so that some trust about the services is developed among users.

People: People, include library and information professionals working in various sections of the library working at different levels, i.e. lower, middle and top, skilled, semi-skilled and unskilled, professional, semi-professionals and nonprofessional. It is the value, belief and approach of employees that will reflect in the organisation they work. The management structure and style must support each employee to give some intangible value to its users-internal and external. People involved in library and information services require good knowledge of both systems and physical resources and must be competent to use their knowledge to create customized offerings to users and an ability to communicate about the value of services to them. In formulating a marketing strategy, the library management has to adapt to its environment as understanding the environment would help the library in not only altering its existing marketing mix but in identifying new opportunities by selecting an appropriate market to serve.

Conclusion

Summing up the study concludes that there is a growing need for understanding and employing marketing in libraries and information services throughout the world. There have been numerous efforts on this area even in developing countries like India. But unplanned growth and the gap between the academics and practitioners hinders the development of the discipline. Emergence of this contemporary area involves enormous opportunities for further research.

Some of which could be visualized are: Tracing the growth of literature: information sources, review of literature, creation of web based resources and databases. Tracing the stage of Library and Information Services marketing with regard to conceptual framework, acceptance, applications and barriers, assessing the role of professional associations and institutions in bringing out marketing orientation in library services. Status of marketing of library services in different kind of libraries and their comparative studies and future improvement. Finding avenues for manpower development. Identifying best practices and making an environment to replicate these. To minimize gap between theory and practices there is a strong need to re-energize researchers, teachers, practitioners, and policy makers to consolidate efforts to develop the marketing of library and information services as an academic discipline.

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